

Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) with 5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde Guanylhydrazone

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Guanylhydrazones form complexes with transition metal ions¹. 5-Chlorosalicylaldehyde guanylhydrazone (CSAG) forms complexes with Pd^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III} etc. in alkaline medium². The present communication deals with the application of CSAG for spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II).

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of Pd^{II}-CSAG complex shows $\lambda_{\max}$ at 400 nm where the reagent has no significant absorption. The molar extinction coefficient was found to be $0.7129 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The complex shows maximum absorbance in the pH range 7.5–9.0, hence further studies are made at pH 8.1. The complex is stable for several hours and about a 2-fold excess of CSAG is necessary to obtain maximum colour intensity. Beer's law is obeyed upto 6.0 ppm Pd. The practical range of determination of palladium obtained from Ringbom's method³ is 3–6 ppm. The Sandell's sensitivity⁴ was found to be $0.07462 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

The composition of Pd^{II}-(CSAG) complex was determined by Job's method⁵ and mole-ratio method⁶. The results indicate the formation of single complex having the composition 1 : 2 (Pd : CSAG). The degree of dissociation was found to be 0.130. The apparent instability constant⁷ is 3.211×10^{-11} .

The interference of various ions was studied. The amount of diverse ion to bring about $\pm 2\%$ variation in absorbance was taken as the tolerance limit. It was observed that Co^{II}, Fe^{III}, Mn^{II}, Cr^{VI} and EDTA interfere.

The proposed method was applied for the determination of Pd^{II} in Ni–Al catalyst and synthetic mixtures. The results (Table 1) are consistent with those obtained by 1-nitroso-2-naphthol photometric method⁸.

Experimental

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 20 spectrophotometer was used. pH was measured on an Elico LI-120 instrument using glass-calomel electrode.

The reagent, CSAG was synthesised by the reported method². Its $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ solution was prepared in distilled ethanol and further dilution was done with distilled water. A standard solution of Pd^{II} (1.0 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared by dissolving palladium(II) chloride (A.R.) in distilled water containing a few ml of concentrated HCl and standardised with dimethylglyoxime gravimetrically⁹. Buffer solutions were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts of disodium hydrogen phosphate and sodium hydroxide. All reagents were of A.R. grade.

Procedure : To an aliquot of solution containing 30–50 μg of Pd^{II}, the reagent (CSAG) solution (0.6–1.0 ml) was added. pH of the solution was adjusted to 8.1 by adding buffer solution and diluted to 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 400 nm against the reagent blank.

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TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Pd IN Ni-AL CATALYST AND SYNTHETIC MIXTURE

Ni-Al catalyst :		Std. method	
Pd%	Proposed method	Pd%	X
0.150		0.152	
0.150		0.153	
0.154	0.153	0.155	0.155
0.155		0.156	
0.156		0.159	
Synthetic mixture* :		Pd found (mg)	
Composition (μg)			
Pd ^{II} (150) + Pt ^{II} (500) + Ir ^{III} (750)		148.90	
Pd ^{II} (100) + Ni ^{II} (150) + Os ^{VIII} (200)		99.80	

*Triplicate analysis.

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